

THE USE OF MEDICINAL PLANTS IN LANDSCAPE ARCHITECTURE PROJECTS IN OUR COUNTRY AND ARTISTIC SOLUTION OF IT

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Abstract. *This article will be devoted to the improvement of town planning in our country using landscape architectural ornamental and medicinal plants.*

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We can see that the need for aesthetic, ecological approaches to the city is increasing significantly nowadays. Toxic gases and climate factors emitted from industrial enterprises and vehicles cause damage to living organisms, significant poisoning of water, soil and biology, and foul odors emitted from waste have a serious impact on atmospheric pollution and human health remains one of the most actual problems of today. If we continue to be careless and apathy to such happenings, it will lead to the poisoning of the clean air which we breathe, causes various diseases of our children and to the occurrence of various changes in their bodies. At this point, if we remember the immortal words "If there were no dust and smoke, mankind would have lived for a thousand years" of our great grandfather Abu Ali Ibn Sina, one of our ancestors who made his unique contribution to the world medicine and known in Europe as Avicenna, we realize that environment is a priceless blessing which is given to mankind.

The absence of an ecologically perfect natural landscape in an urbanized environment does not help to restore the mental and physical balance of humanity, but on the contrary provokes mental illnesses.

After studying these problems based on the decision №322 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan which was adopted in December 29, 2010 the program of strengthening the material and technical base of cultural and recreation centers for 2011-2015 and further improving their activities was approved by higher organizational institutions. According to the program for 2011-2015, it is envisaged to create conditions for cultural recreation of the population by gradually reconstructing cultural and recreation parks, which are necessary for cultural recreation of the population, especially for children and youth. In this regard, according to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers №223 of August 13, 2013, the program for the development of landscape design in the Republic of Uzbekistan was approved. The purpose of this program is to improve the architectural and artistic appearance of settlements and inter-residential areas.

Greening of the city plays a major role in establishing ecological, planned urban planning, socio-economic and aesthetic relations of landscape architecture. Since the art form of landscape architecture is considered a new concept for us, it is clear that some questions will arise such as what is the landscape itself in many people's minds? What subjects does it include? What is its

task? Let's first talk about the word Landscape: The term Landscape appeared a hundred years ago. Associated with the emergence of national parks in the United States. The word **Landscape** is a German word, **Land**-land,ground, **schaft** –landscape,scenery, which means the scenery of earth(landscape) or scenic land. Landscape consists of natural elements in an open environment and is related to climate, topography, water, soil, flora and fauna.

Typically, landscapes are divided into **natural** and **anthropogenic** landscapes. A **natural landscape** is a landscape that is formed or being formed only under the influence of natural factors, which is not affected by human activity. **Anthropogenic landscape** (landscape affected by human activity) is a landscape formed and being formed under the influence of natural and anthropogenic factors. In landscape architecture, engineering structures, artificial water bodies, roads, pavements, boulevards, objects of artistic and decorative arts, construction technology, agrotechnics and artificial elements of the landscape are widely used, which are closely connected and form integrated compositions. Two types of lighting are used in landscape composition: Solar and artificial lighting. Planted plants must also be placed in their order: flowering season, color, height, etc. are should be taken into consideration.

Landscape architecture-is the formation of an artistic appearance of the environment with the help of natural and artificial architectural devices and elements, theoretical basis of architectural activity and landscape creation.

Landscape design - a project designed to create landscape objects of various appearance; it is a type of creative activity aimed at creating artificial elements of landscape objects according to specific functions based on artistic aesthetic and ecological conditions. Landscape architecture works together with floristry, soil science, geology, climate, relief, watersheds, geography, sculpture and other sectors. Landscaping and Landscape Architecture will be better by improving the environment, increasing economic stability, ensuring population growth, improving the habitat change. The creation of a whole composition by combining landscape architecture with relief, water, plants and decorative means was included in the experiments carried out in foreign countries. Similar experiments are being carried out in our country, and the result shows that the main goal of landscape architecture is to harmonize the functional, ecological and aesthetic qualities of the city. In the use of Introductory (Acclimatization of plants which were brought from foreign countries) plants and plants with a medicinal aspect greatly contributes to the economic stability of our country and a more attractive appearance of the city. Medicinal plants are not only for pharmaceutical purposes, but also attract people with their unique flowers and scenic views. Our Uzbekistan has very fertile soils and we can meet various types of local plants. More than 1200 medicinal plants grow in our country and they are widely used in traditional medicine. According to the World Health Organization, 60% of the available medicines are preparations obtained from medicinal plant raw materials.

At present measures have been taken to increase the species of medicinal plants and protect them, and laws and decisions have been adopted by higher organizations. If we make it a tradition to use medicinal plants in urban landscaping, it would be good job. Such plants consist of trees, bushes, semi-shrubs and ground covers.

In order to preserve the diversity of the species composition of the flora in Uzbekistan, a number of laws and decisions were adopted by our state: laws such as on December 9, 1992 "On the protection of nature", May 7, 1993 "On extremely important protected natural areas", December 26, 1997 "On the use of plants and their protection"; the decision of the Cabinet of

Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan №508 adopted on October 28, 2004, "On strengthening control over export and import outside the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, rational use of biological resources" and others.

Ensuring the implementation of 19 paragraph of Memorandum of the meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan № 40 dated on February 17, 2014 "On the role, personal responsibility and accountability of all heads of state administration in ensuring the implementation of the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees, decisions and orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and 1.12 paragraph of the memorandum of the meeting dated on January 2015, № 5 "On measures to further expand the development of the forestry system, cultivation, preparation and processing of medicinal and nutritious plant raw materials in 2015-2017", Description, distribution, preparation of raw materials of medicinal plants that exist naturally and culturally in the Republic, and the suggestion of wide use of medicinal plants and herbs in urban landscaping in our country, to increase their chemical composition and use in medicine, and to get the best results in the future. It would be expedient to introduce the use of local decorative medicinal plants in urban landscaping. One of the main reasons for this is to illuminate the landscape composition solution of the city from medicinal plants that are disappearing and are not used in medicine and to present the tourists visiting our country the medicinal and decorative plants, to rejuvenate our city and increase the number of beaches, to promote medicinal plants in foreign countries as much as possible.

Using medicinal plants we can create landscape compositions that supports people with high spirits . For example, it is possible to create shapes from the boxwood plant in the tapiar method, and to create elegant compositions using the landscape or satiler methods from plants such as ordinary Igir, origanum vulgare, Medicinal marigold, and medicinal chamomile. It is worth praising such beauties created by the unceasing research of man and the hard work of his hands. Landscape architecture has a special place in the prosperity of our city.

In conclusion, it is worth mentioning that according to the information of psychologists, with the intention of increasing and preserving such decorative and at the same time medicinal plants, the creation and reproduction of landscape design compositions of various forms, with the intention of preserving them, it has been found that it can have a great positive effect can relieve a person of stress, give birth to a healthy child, and increase the age of the population . In this context, the creation and construction of cultural recreation grounds is considered one of the most important tasks being carried out nowadays.

Engineering structures, artificial water bodies in landscape architecture, roads, pavements, avenues, objects of artistic decorative art, construction technology, agrotechnics and artificial elements of the landscape are widely used, they form a whole composition if they are closely connected. Landscape Two types of lighting are used in the composition: Solar and artificial lighting. Planted plants must also be placed in their order: flowering season, color, height, etc. are taken into account.

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